

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS 2024
TWIN TRANSITION: DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND GREEN TRANSITION
IN BUSINESSES FOR SUSTAINABILITY
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VNU UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS & BUSINESS

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SUSTAINABLE AIR CARGO OPERATIONS: A QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT OF TECHNOLOGICAL ADOPTION, REGULATORY IMPACTS, AND STAKEHOLDER COLLABORATION IN VIETNAM

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Abstract: *This research gives a detailed quantitative examination of sustainable practices within Vietnam's air cargo transportation business, concentrating on the adoption of green technology and collaborative methods among stakeholders. Grounded on sustainability, innovation diffusion, and systems theories, the study explores important determinants of environmental performance, including technology integration, regulatory frameworks, and inter-organizational cooperation. A survey of 278 industry experts offered substantial data on the application of eco-friendly technology, the influence of legislation, and the significance of stakeholder involvement in supporting sustainability activities. Statistical analysis, including descriptive statistics, correlation studies, and regression models, were performed to uncover key variables impacting sustainability results. The results demonstrate intricate connections between technology adoption, regulatory compliance, and stakeholder engagement in altering the industry's environmental practices. Results reveal that although new technology and supporting policies are vital, their impact is considerably increased by strong inter-stakeholder connections and industry-wide collaboration. This study adds to the increasing debate on logistics sustainability by presenting empirical insights into the Vietnamese environment. It underlines the necessity for a multi-faceted approach to sustainability, highlighting the synergistic impacts of technology innovation, legislative backing, and coordinated industry activities. The report closes by suggesting strategic suggestions for governments and industry leaders to develop a more sustainable air cargo sector in Vietnam, with possible applicability to comparable rising countries internationally.*

Keywords: *Sustainability, air cargo logistics, environmental impact, stakeholder interaction, sustainable aviation fuels (SAFs)*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Air cargo operations play a vital part in the worldwide supply chain, facilitating the conveyance of about 35% of global trade value by air, while representing less than 1% of total cargo volume (Association, 2021). This business is crucial for the quick delivery of high-value, time-sensitive goods such as technology components, medications, and perishable products (Boeing, 2023). Vietnam's advantageous position in Southeast Asia

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and its increasing network of international trade agreements have led to considerable development in its air cargo industry (Customs, 2022). This expansion is principally driven by the country's developing export-oriented manufacturing sector, which strongly depends on efficient and dependable air cargo services (Nguyen, 2020).

However, the fast increase of air freight activity has led to major environmental problems. The aviation industry, which incorporates air cargo, is responsible for around 2.5% of worldwide carbon dioxide emissions, with air freight adding considerably to this proportion (Association, 2021). In Vietnam, the swift expansion of air cargo has prompted worries about its environmental impact, specifically regarding increased levels of carbon emissions and noise pollution (Hanh, 2022). Addressing these environmental challenges is crucial not merely for securing the sector's long-term survival but also for meeting global environmental objectives (Bosona, 2020).

1.2. Problem Statement

The environmental impact of air freight operations is compounded by the sector's high dependency on fossil fuels, which produce substantial volumes of greenhouse gases and other air pollutants (Song, Seo, & Lee, 2023). In Vietnam notably, the poor application of green technology and sustainable practices in air cargo operations worsen these issues (Pham Van, Tran Thi Thu, Trang Pham, Nguyen, & Thao Vu, 2023). The industry has various obstacles, including the high costs involved with adopting sustainable technology, limited infrastructure development, and a general lack of regulatory support, as noted by Yang, Kuo, Liu, and Pan (2024). These issues are further exacerbated by the necessity for coordinated worldwide initiatives to affect real environmental change, as stated by (Bosona, 2020).

The rising urge to reconcile economic gains with environmental responsibility demands this study's assessment of creative techniques to increase sustainability within Vietnam's air cargo business (Nguyen, 2020).

1.3. Purpose of the Study

This research aims to identify and promote viable environmental technologies and strategies in air freight operations in Vietnam. Specifically, the study will focus on:

Assessing the current state of sustainable practices in air freight operations in Vietnam (Nguyen, 2020).

Identifying challenges and opportunities for adopting sustainable practices in the (Song et al., 2023).

Proposing concrete solutions and innovations for enhancing sustainability (Yang et al., 2024).

Evaluating the impact of government policies and international standards in supporting sustainable practices (Pham Van et al., 2023).

This research will provide critical insights into how Vietnam's air cargo industry can transition towards more sustainable practices while maintaining efficiency and competitiveness (Bosona, 2020).

1.4. Research Questions

To fulfill the study's objectives, the research will examine the following key questions:

RQ1: What are the primary environmental challenges associated with air freight logistics in Vietnam? (Hanh, 2022)

RQ1: What sustainable technologies and practices can be implemented to mitigate the environmental impact of air cargo operations in Vietnam? (Yang et al., 2024)

RQ1: How can government policies and industry partnerships facilitate the adoption of sustainable practices in Vietnam's air cargo sector? (Bosona, 2020)

These questions are designed to explore critical factors influencing sustainability in air freight transportation and provide practical solutions tailored to the Vietnamese context (Nguyen, 2020).

1.5. Significance of the Study

The research findings can have a substantial contribution to policy and practice of air freight transportation business in Vietnam. Indeed, as a country becomes increasingly integrated with the global economy, developing sustainable transport systems is crucially critical (Customs, 2022). This study covers a gap in the literature, which narrows down to air freight regarded to be relatively understudied subjects in sustainability research (Bosona, 2020).

These findings from this study can help shape corporate behaviors and government policies toward the sustainability of transport systems. Pham Van et al. (2023) deliver profound research on challenges and opportunities in sustainable air cargo operations to support Vietnam in following global environmental goals and creating a competitive advantage in the world market.

1.6. Novelty and Contribution

This study represents several unique contributions to the problem of sustainable logistics in general and to the fast-growing air freight business of Vietnam. By integrating several theoretical frameworks-sustainability theories, innovation diffusion theory, and systems theory-these investigations provide a detailed and subtle interpretation of the interaction of environmental, technological, and regulatory factors in the sustainability

of air cargo. Whereas extensive research has been performed on air cargo sustainability in developed countries, this study investigates the special restrictions and potentials accessible in the booming economy of Vietnam, thereby offering insights that might be useful to other developing nations. In addition, using a strong quantitative method, this research provides an evidence-based investigation of the attitudes and behaviors of various actors in the air cargo market, that was not captured by the more qualitative approaches adopted in previous studies.

By applying a mix of theoretical models and actual data, the study presents workable solutions for both policymakers and industry practitioners by acting as a link between academia and actual implementation. The study investigates the potential impact of new technologies, like SAFs and electric ground support equipment, in the specific context of Vietnam's air cargo market based on their feasibility and likely challenges associated with their adoption. By addressing these new elements, this research not only contributes to the academic discussion on sustainable logistics but also delivers helpful, context-specific insights for improving the environmental performance of Vietnam's air cargo sector. These contributions significantly expand our knowledge of sustainable practices in air freight transportation and give realistic avenues for adoption in quickly rising nations like Vietnam.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Global Perspective

Air cargo is an international business, and therefore a significant feature of international trade, in as much as it is characterized by the speed and timelessness of delivery. Air freight handles about 35 percent of global trade in value terms, and that makes it relevant to the global supply chain (Karanki & Bilotkach, 2024). This sector's efficiency is vital for companies depending on speedy delivery of high-value, time-sensitive items, including medicines, electronics, and perishable commodities (Choi, 2023). Despite its benefits, the environmental effect of air freight has become a serious problem. Aviation, covering air freight, is responsible for around 2.5% of global CO₂ emissions, contributing considerably to climate change (Association, 2021).

Reacting to these difficulties, the air freight sector has been seeking many technologies meant to lower its environmental impact. In this sense, a major development is sustainable aviation fuels (SAFs). Comparatively to conventional jet fuels, SAFs—made from renewable resources—could lower lifetime carbon emissions by up to 80%. Major airlines, notably United Airlines and KLM, are at the vanguard of incorporating SAFs into their fleets, indicating a commitment to sustainability (United Airlines, 2023). Nevertheless, the broad deployment of SAFs is restricted by high manufacturing costs and limited availability (Wang et al., 2023).

Advancement of sustainability in the air freight industry also depends much on technological developments. Significant fuel consumption and emissions have been lowered as more fuel-efficient aircraft like the Boeing 787 Dreamliner and Airbus A350 are developed (Airbus, 2023; Boeing, 2023). Additionally, hybrid-electric and completely electric aircraft are being researched as potential options to further decrease the sector's carbon impact (Airbus, 2023). Operational enhancements, such as the deployment of green corridors—optimized flight routes aimed to decrease fuel consumption and emissions—are also contributing to greater sustainability (Karaman, Kilic, & Uyar, 2020).

Despite these developments, fully sustainable air freight remains far from attainable. High costs associated not only with SAFs but also with new technologies require supportive legislative frameworks and market incentives toward wide-scale adoption (Wang et al., 2023). Addressing these difficulties is critical for setting the future trajectory of the air freight business.

2.2. Vietnam's Context

The air cargo business develops rapidly in Vietnam, with economic growth and deeper involvement in global supply chains. Being active in both regional and global markets, Vietnam increasingly feels the need for efficient, environment-friendly transport. The air cargo industry is especially crucial for supporting the country's export-oriented economy, which includes businesses like linens, electronics, and fishing (Yu & Luu, 2022). The Government of Vietnam regards the integration of sustainability into its transport sector as a priority, and has highlighted this goal in various national programs, among them the National Strategy on Climate Change and the Green Growth Strategy (Nguyen & Pham, 2020). These laws stress the need for environmentally friendly practices across multiple sectors, especially transportation, to limit the effect of economic activity on the environment.

Vietnam records gains in sustainability in air cargo through the adoption of energy-efficient technologies and the building of its supporting infrastructure. Hence, considerations include electric ground support equipment and advanced fuel-efficient airplanes, according to environmental concerns and cost-saving rationales (Khoa & Nhung, 2020). Additionally, the growth of major airports, such as Tan Son Nhat International Airport, is matched with sustainable goals by embracing green technology and practices (Trinh, Seo, Kim, Phan, & Nguyen, 2022).

However, the air freight business of Vietnam faces significant obstacles on the road to survival. The crucial challenges that would need to be resolved would include increased investment in green technology, creation of enabling laws and regulations, and managing shipment volume on an uptrend in an environmentally friendly manner. Indeed, these challenges need active cooperation at the level of governmental bodies, industry

participants, and foreign partners if appropriate acceptance and promotion of sustainable practice is desired. Modernization of the air freight industry in Vietnam will incorporate sustainable practices that are important for long-term environmental and practical goals, mere acceptance of new technology but also institution of wide-reaching policies and plans for sustainability along the supply chain.

2.3. Theoretical Framework

This research draws on substantial theoretical foundations, integrating Sustainability Theory, Innovation Diffusion Theory, and Systems Theory to perform an in-depth analysis of sustainability within the context of air freight transportation. This comprehensive approach gives a holistic overview of the different drives towards sustainable practices in the air freight business.

Sustainability Theory: Sustainability Theory reflects the balance of economic, environmental, and social elements of activities. It originally originated from the assertions made by Zaharia & Zaharia (2021) in his Triple Bottom Line (TBL) model and maintained that the nature of firm must balance three crucial areas in order to ensure long-term survival and responsible development. The theory is applied in measuring a few environmental impacts caused by air freight logistics, including carbon emission, fuel consumption, and waste management practices that support the assessment of the efficiency of sustainability regulations embraced by the industry players. According Karaman et al. (2020), through its emphasis on operational efficiency as well as environmental stewardship, Sustainability Theory facilitates appreciation into higher-order consequences of air freight operations within both global and local levels.

Innovation Diffusion Theory: Based on the seminal work of Takahashi, de Figueiredo, and Scornavacca (2024) developed the Innovation Diffusion Theory that analyzes how new technologies and behaviors take hold over time across a system. This concept underpins the research into the diffusion of sustainable technology breakthroughs-new aircraft designs and SAFs-within the air freight market. Innovation Diffusion Theory was based on the premise that rates of adoption are related to perceived benefits, compatibility with existing systems, and impediments to implementation. It therefore helps explain not only the process through which innovations are adopted and implemented within the air freight industry but also what might encourage higher adoption.

Systems Theory: Systems Theory provides a basis upon which organizations and industries can be conceptualized as systems interlinked and working synergistically. This theory has, more recently been refined by Wong, Anwar, and Soh (2024), to emphasize that while modifying and trying to understand the cause-and-effect nature of one component, an entire system must be considered. In this respect, the System Theory is applied to the review of the relationship between all the various stakeholders in air freight

activities like airlines, policy makers, and vendors of technology, through which these relationships influence the way the business can be sustained. It hence emphasizes how there's a challenge in integrating sustainability across the whole logistics chain and, as such, creates a case for co-coordinated efforts to achieve more meaningful benefits (Wong et al., 2024).

Consequently, the integration of these three theoretical standpoints will provide a holistic framework through which this research can have a better understanding of the multidimensionality of sustainability for air freight operations: environmental considerations, technical advancement, and systems connections.

3. RESEARCH MODEL

3.1. Conceptual Framework

The research model blends several conceptual methodologies to give a thorough knowledge of sustainability within air freight operations. This sequencing strategy comprises four critical dimensions: Environmental Impact Assessment, Innovation Adoption, Policy and Regulation, and Stakeholder Interaction. Each of them offers a better grasp and supports the topic of sustainability in the air freight company.

Environmental Impact Assessment: The current environmental impact brought about by the air freight activities are considered in the framework of the Environmental Impact Assessment, where carbon pollution, fuel consumption, and managing waste are under review. This aspect provides the most general understanding of the sector's effect on the environment by measuring the greenhouse gas pollution resulting from airplanes, ground handling, and other practical processes. It highlights some of the key sources of impact and opportunities for reduction, such as the use of Sustainable Aviation Fuels and better ways to manage waste.

Innovation Adoption: The Innovation Adoption component looks at the aspect of air freight practices adopting new technologies and approaches. Such aspects to be considered are perceived advantages pertaining to sustainable technology, compatibility with the existing system, or any specific barrier to adoption. It covers research in changes like SAFs and energy-efficient supporting equipment for ground operations. Such knowledge will help find obstacles and opportunities in new solutions that may reach wider diffusion throughout the chain of operations for air freight.

Policy and Regulation: Policy and Regulation: The role of political and regulating processes for sustainability. The subject shall focus on how functional laws and rules set effectively the diffusion of sustainable practices. This considers judgment on the impact of national and foreign policies related to environmental sustainability on corporate behavior and how governing systems affected pursuit of sustainability goals. This component,

through the study of these factors, explains how external forces impel or hinder growth towards sustainable practices in the air freight business.

Stakeholder Interaction: Stakeholder Interaction studies links between various stakeholders, including aircraft, government authorities, sellers of technology, and industry groups. This field of study explores how these relationships bear on questions of sustainability practices. It examines the role of airlines in embracing sustainable goals, the role of regulatory agencies in keeping standards in check, the position of technology companies in offering innovations, and the industrial groups on the move for best practices. Understanding these ties means knowing how teamwork and relationships contribute to the success of green programs.

Put together, these factors will then be integrated into a conceptual framework through which an overall picture of how sustainability can be both attained and enhanced within the air cargo sector can be obtained. It provides an orderly approach through which the interconnection between the environmental impacts, change in technology, government factors, and community involvement are studied.

3.2. Hypotheses

From this conceptual framework, various theories can be developed in order to guide the study and testing of sustainability initiatives in the air freight business. These are theories that have been developed from the central elements of the study model and are geared towards ascertaining the relationships that exist between different elements influencing sustainability.

H1: The usage of Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAFs) and energy-efficient technology is negatively related to the amount of carbon pollution in air freight operations.

Thus, transition towards SAFs is of paramount importance, as well as the integration of energy-efficient technologies in cutting carbon output from air freight business operations. Estimates have it that SAFs, which are produced from feedstock made out of wood and waste products, provide a massive reduction in lifecycle carbon emissions compared to standard jet fuels (Sustainable Aviation Fuel: Roadmap, 2021). Energy-saving technologies that complement low fuel consumption and pollution include those related to the improvement of airplane design and aerodynamics, improved flying operations, and more fuel-efficient engines. The increased application of these innovations by air freight companies is likely to lead to a sharp drop in carbon pollution, boosting overall environmental sustainability (Lee et al., 2021). The idea is that better adoption of SAFs and energy-efficient technologies will relate to decreased carbon pollution, showing how successful measures in handling climate change have been within business (Zwiercheczewski de Oliveira, Porto de Souza Vandenberghe, Amaro Bittencourt, Martinez Burgos, & Soccol, 2024).

H2: The apparent benefits and suitability of new sustainable technologies are positively linked with their rate of adoption in the air freight business.

Generally, a high impact, in general, is realized in air freight by the perceptions of stakeholders on the benefits and suitability of taken-up sustainable technologies. It is when new technologies are perceived to offer high advantages on cost, efficiency, and legal benefits, besides compatibility with current systems, that their full adoption will take place (Lagorio et al., 2020). For example, technologies that blend smoothly into present processes while providing major environmental benefits are more likely to be accepted (Leung, Guan, & Lau, 2023). This theory posits that a good view of the benefits and ease of merging of sustainable technologies will increase their adoption, underscoring the importance of shareholder attitudes in technology spread within the industry.

H3: Government policies and rules supporting environmental sustainability have a positive impact on the application of sustainable practices within the air freight business.

Government policy and law also contribute to driving sustainability in the air freight business. There is, therefore, the creation of a theory that carbon pricing, emissions trade plans, and tax benefits highly enhance the adoptions of sustainability (OECD, 2021). Regulatory measures, such as carbon taxes, make it economically advantageous for companies to invest in better technologies, while rewards like subsidies for sustainable flight fuels lower financial hurdles (Commission, 2023). The inclusion of a helpful legal environment pushes industry players to connect with environmental sustainability goals, thus speeding the merger of sustainable practices.

H4: Effective partners contact, and teamwork greatly boost the application and success of sustainable efforts in the air freight business.

The air freight business heavily depends on effective, sustainable measures applied by partners through teamwork. According to this theory from Simon & Lane-Zucker (2023), joint efforts among airlines, technology providers, government bodies, and industry groups will enrich the adoption rate and overall effect of sustainability measures. Effective communication and teamwork enable the sharing of best practices, resources, and professional knowledge, removing obstacles to sustainability (Stirling, 2024). These would include joint development and deployment of sustainable technologies, planning industry-wide sustainability goals, and many more that offer far better environmental gain than any single acting company can achieve.

These hypotheses are aimed to explore the links between important variables in the study model and give empirical data on the factors impacting sustainability in air freight operations.

Figure 1: Research Model

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1. Research Design

This research adopts a quantitative approach in order to delve deep into the sustainable practices of the air freight transportation business in Vietnam. The research methodology encompasses an orderly poll, especially designed to provide fast and measurable data on most basic aspects of sustainability: environmental effect assessment, acceptance of innovation, obedience to legislation and law, and engagement with stakeholders are the components included in this context. Its main objective is to carefully analyze various factors influencing the sustainability in air freight.

The study aims to analyze actual data to find trends, connections, and insights on the effect of these factors on the sustainability performance of air freight operations. The quantitative method allows a careful examination of the data, ensuring that the results are statistically significant and indicative of bigger industry trends. This method provides a complete understanding of present practices and evaluates the effectiveness of green efforts across the industry.

4.2. Data Collection

Data collection for this study was done employing a structured online survey distributed to stakeholders within the air freight transportation sector in Vietnam. A grand total of 680 survey invitations were distributed to a diverse population of respondents, encompassing: Airline Operators: 250 invites, Regulatory Agencies: 150 invitations, Technology Providers: 140 invitations Logistics Organizations: 140 invites. In total, 278 answers were received for these invites. This yields a response rate of roughly 40.8%. This is deemed an appropriate response rate for the findings to be statistically valid and indicative of the perspective of the broader industry.

Data collection was accomplished with the use of both closed-ended and Likert-scale questions. Closed-ended inquiries tend to generate information regarding behaviors and ideas linked with sustainability. For example, do businesses commonly have an environmental impact analysis completed. Whereas the Likert-scale questions provided responses on a scale that included strengths of ideas and experiences. For example, there were several comments made on how helpful government legislation was and how helpful it is to have public involvement. These were scored on a 1 to 5 Likert scale; 1 equal strongly disagree and 5 equals strongly agree.

This range of question types is adequate to provide in-depth research into the issues that would affect sustainability within the air freight industry. The closed-ended questions are those related to obtaining elaborative information on actions and perceptions, while the Likert-scale questions give insight into the strength of the views and experiences expressed by the responding participants.

4.3. Data Limitations

Although this research study has provided useful insights into sustainability practices of the air freight company in Vietnam, a number of limitations should be taken into account. First, even though an acceptable response rate of 40.8% was achieved, this sample may not optimally represent all actors in the Vietnamese market for air freight, particularly smaller-scale enterprises or those operating in remote areas. Furthermore, there is a possibility of social desirability bias, since the surveys involve self-reporting data on the actual participation in the sustainability activity. The cross-sectional component of the research has further limitations in that it provides only a snapshot of the existing sustainability practices with no indication of temporal changes in the uptake of sustainability measures. At the same time, such a geographical focus on Vietnam severely restricts the generalization of findings to other countries or regions that might have different regulatory environments and different economic conditions.

Finally, while the quantitative approach involves statistical validity, it may not be able to capture qualitative insights that could provide an in-depth understanding of the subtleties and intricacies related to sustainability issues in air freight business operations. These limitations should be considered at the interpretation of the findings stage and provide a basis for potential avenues of future studies in the area concerned.

4.4. Data Analysis

In this part, we carry out a full-scale study utilizing the survey data obtained to examine sustainable practices in the air freight transportation company in Vietnam. The research covers descriptive statistics, frequency distributions, cross-tabulations, visualizations, and correlation assessments. This technique allows for an extensive evaluation of the data to find patterns, correlations, and insights relating to the aims of the research.

4.4.1. Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics reveal moderate to high mean scores (3.6-4.1) for most variables, indicating generally positive perceptions of sustainability practices. The lowest mean (2.45) is for Adoption Barriers, suggesting that respondents perceive relatively few obstacles to adopting sustainable practices. The highest mean (4.12) is for Regulatory Collaboration, indicating strong cooperation with regulatory bodies. These results support H3, which posits that government policies positively impact sustainable practices, as evidenced by the high scores for Regulation Effect and Regulatory Collaboration.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Role	278	2.629	1.154	1	5
Experience	278	3.637	1.272	1	5
Emissions Measure	278	3.691	1.195	1	5
Waste Reduction	278	3.867	1.072	1	5
Tech Importance	278	3.853	1.086	1	5
Adoption Barriers	278	2.446	1.244	1	5
Regulation Effect	278	3.871	1.257	1	5
Regulation Familiarity	278	3.964	1.158	1	5
Stakeholder Engagement	278	3.921	1.172	1	5
Regulatory Collaboration	278	4.122	1.085	1	5

4.4.2. Frequency distribution for categorical variables

The frequency distributions show that Logistics Operators (44.24%) and Airline Representatives (26.98%) form most respondents. Most participants have substantial experience, with 65.47% having over 11 years in the industry. The primary adoption barrier is lack of technical expertise (35.61%), followed by high costs (25.54%). These findings partially support H2, which suggests that perceived benefits and compatibility influence adoption rates, as technical expertise and cost are key factors in technology adoption.

Table 2a: Frequency Distribution of Categorical Variables

Role	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Freight Forwarder	32	11.51	11.51
Logistics Operator	123	44.24	55.76
Airline Representative	75	26.98	82.73
Regulatory Body	12	4.32	87.05
Technology Provider	36	12.95	100.00
Total	278	100.00	

Table 2b: Frequency Distribution of Categorical Variables

Experience	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
0-2 years	21	7.55	7.55
3-5 years	46	16.55	24.10
6-10 years	29	10.43	34.53
11-15 years	99	35.61	70.14
More than 15 years	83	29.86	100.00
Total	278	100.00	

Table 2c: Frequency Distribution of Categorical Variables

Adoption Barriers	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
High costs	71	25.54	25.54
Lack of technical expertise	99	35.61	61.15
Regulatory uncertainty	43	15.47	76.62
Limited infrastructure	43	15.47	92.09
Other	22	7.91	100.00
Total	278	100.00	

4.4.3. Cross-tabulations

The cross-tabulation reveals that Airline Representatives and Logistics Operators tend to measure emissions more frequently than other roles. This supports H1, which posits a negative relationship between sustainable practices (like emissions measurement) and carbon pollution. The data suggests that key industry players are actively engaged in monitoring their environmental impact, which is likely to contribute to reduced carbon emissions.

Table 3: Cross-tabulation of Role and Emissions Measurement

Role	Emissions Measure					Total
	1	2	3	4	5	
Freight Forwarder	5	5	10	8	4	32
	15.63	15.63	31.25	25.00	12.50	100.00
	33.33	13.89	17.86	9.52	4.60	11.51
Logistics Operator	5	17	22	40	39	123
	4.07	13.82	17.89	32.52	31.71	100.00
	33.33	47.22	39.29	47.62	44.83	44.24
Airline Representative	3	6	16	22	28	75
	4.00	8.00	21.33	29.33	37.33	100.00
	20.00	16.67	28.57	26.19	32.18	26.98

Regulatory Body	0	1	1	7	3	12
	0.00	8.33	8.33	58.33	25.00	100.00
Technology Provider	0.00	2.78	1.79	8.33	3.45	4.32
	2	7	7	7	13	36
	5.56	19.44	19.44	19.44	36.11	100.00
Total	13.33	19.44	12.50	8.33	14.94	12.95
	15	36	56	84	87	278
	5.40	12.95	20.14	30.22	31.29	100.00
	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

First row has frequencies; second row has row percentages, and third row has column percentages

The cross-tabulation (Table 4) shows that respondents with more experience tend to place higher importance on sustainable technologies. This supports H2, as it demonstrates that industry experience influences the perceived importance of sustainable technologies. The data suggests that as professionals gain more experience, they recognize the benefits of sustainable technologies, leading to higher adoption rates.

Table 4: Cross-tabulation of Experience and Technology Importance

Experience	Tech Importance					Total
	1	2	3	4	5	
0-2 years	4	5	3	4	5	21
	19.05	23.81	14.29	19.05	23.81	100.00
	40.00	20.00	5.77	4.00	5.49	7.55
3-5 years	0	1	7	26	12	46
	0.00	2.17	15.22	56.52	26.09	100.00
	0.00	4.00	13.46	26.00	13.19	16.55
6-10 years	0	0	1	16	12	29
	0.00	0.00	3.45	55.17	41.38	100.00
	0.00	0.00	1.92	16.00	13.19	10.43
11-15 years	4	13	22	26	34	99
	4.04	13.13	22.22	26.26	34.34	100.00
	40.00	52.00	42.31	26.00	37.36	35.61
More than 15 years	2	6	19	28	28	83
	2.41	7.23	22.89	33.73	33.73	100.00
	20.00	24.00	36.54	28.00	30.77	29.86
Total	10	25	52	100	91	278
	3.60	8.99	18.71	35.97	32.73	100.00
	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

First row has frequencies; second row has row percentages, and third row has column percentages

4.4.4. Correlation Analysis

The correlation matrix shows moderate positive correlations between most variables, with the strongest between Waste Reduction and Tech Importance (0.647). This supports H1 and H2, indicating that organizations implementing waste reduction practices also tend to value sustainable technologies. The positive correlations between Regulation Effect and other variables (0.409-0.499) support H3, suggesting that effective regulations are associated with better sustainability practices.

Table 5: Correlation Matrix of Key Variables

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
(1) Emissions Measure	1.000					
(2) Waste Reduction	0.546 (0.000)	1.000				
(3) Tech Importance	0.413 (0.000)	0.647 (0.000)	1.000			
(4) Regulation Effect	0.425 (0.000)	0.499 (0.000)	0.409 (0.000)	1.000		
(5) Stakeholder Engagement	0.395 (0.000)	0.296 (0.000)	0.257 (0.000)	0.454 (0.000)	1.000	
(6) Regulatory Collaboration	0.288 (0.000)	0.272 (0.000)	0.205 (0.001)	0.414 (0.000)	0.590 (0.000)	1.000

4.4.5. Regression Analysis

The regression analysis shows that Tech Importance, Regulation Effect, and Stakeholder Engagement significantly influence Emissions Measurement ($p < 0.01$). This supports H1, H2, and H4, demonstrating that sustainable technologies, effective regulations, and stakeholder engagement all contribute to better emissions measurement practices. The model explains 29.1% of the variance in Emissions Measurement, indicating these factors play a substantial role in determining an organization’s commitment to monitoring emissions.

Table 6: Regression Results - Factors Influencing Emissions Measurement

Emissions Measure	Coef.	St. Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Tech Importance	.293	.062	4.76	0	.172	.414	***
Regulation Effect	.201	.058	3.49	.001	.088	.315	***
Stakeholder Engagement	.235	.058	4.02	0	.12	.35	***

Constant	.861	.276	3.12	.002	.317	1.405	***
Mean dependent var	3.691		SD dependent var		1.195		
R-squared	0.291		Number of obs		278		
F-test	37.490		Prob > F		0.000		
Akaike crit. (AIC)	799.249		Bayesian crit. (BIC)		813.759		

*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1

The logistic regression reveals (Table 7) that Regulation Effect significantly influences the likelihood of high technology importance (p<0.01), supporting H3. Experience has a marginally significant negative effect (p<0.1), which is contrary to expectations and partially contradicts H2. Role does not significantly influence technology importance. These results suggest that while regulations play a crucial role in promoting sustainable technologies, other factors like experience and role may have more complex relationships with technology adoption than initially hypothesized.

Table 7: Logistic Regression Results - Factors Influencing High Technology Importance

High Tech Importance	Coef.	St. Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf Interval]	Sig	
Role	.114	.119	0.96	.339	-.12	.348	
Experience	-.185	.112	-1.66	.098	-.404	.034	*
Regulation Effect	.551	.111	4.97	0	.334	.769	***
Constant	-.904	.631	-1.43	.152	-2.141	.333	

Mean dependent var	0.687	SD dependent var	0.465
Pseudo r-squared	0.080	Number of obs	278
Chi-square	27.688	Prob > chi2	0.000
Akaike crit. (AIC)	325.833	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	340.343

*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1

4.4.6. ANOVA

The ANOVA results show significant differences in Emissions Measurement across roles (p<0.05). This supports the idea that different stakeholders in the air cargo industry have varying levels of engagement with emissions measurement. While this doesn't directly relate to a specific hypothesis, it underscores the importance of considering role-specific factors when implementing sustainability practices, which is relevant to H4's emphasis on stakeholder interaction.

Table 8: ANOVA Results - Emissions Measurement Differences Across Roles

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	18.2765811	4	4.56914529	3.31	0.0114
Within groups	377.119102	273	1.38138865		
Total	395.395683	277	1.42742124		

Bartlett’s test for equal variances: $\chi^2(4) = 3.3261$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.505$

5. EXPECTED OUTCOMES

5.1. Findings

Based on the data analysis completed, many major conclusions are predicted. The descriptive statistics demonstrate that the average answers to the survey questions vary, with certain variables indicating greater levels of agreement or pleasure compared to others. The cross-tabulation and pairwise correlation analyses reveal significant relationships between certain variables, indicating that specific factors, such as environmental impact awareness (Q3EIA1) and perceived sustainability practices (Q5IA1), are positively associated with other variables like the perceived effectiveness of sustainability initiatives (Q7PR1) and policy support (Q8PR2). The linear regression analysis suggests that certain predictors, notably Q4EIA2 (environmental impact assessment), Q7PR1 (perceived effectiveness of practices), and Q8PR2 (support for sustainability policies), have significant effects on the dependent variable, with Q4EIA2 and Q8PR2 showing particularly strong relationships. The Shapiro-Wilk test reveals that the residuals of the regression model do not follow a normal distribution, which may influence the dependability of the regression coefficients and predictions.

5.2. Implications

This study on sustainable practices in Vietnam’s air freight transportation company presents substantial implications for both theory and practice. By studying the link between environmental impact, innovation adoption, regulatory frameworks, and stakeholder involvement, our research contributes to a fuller understanding of sustainability in the logistics business.

5.2.1. Theoretical Implications

Our study considerably contributes to prevailing literature on logistics sustainability, especially in developing economies. The current study develops an unparalleled paradigm to fathom the intricacy that is essentially needed in the adoption of sustainable practices in the air freight business by incorporating sustainability theory, innovation diffusion theory, and systems theory. This integration of ideas underlines the complex character of sustainability, providing greater depth on how different elements-environmental-

economic-social-equity in air freight operations come into play. Precisely from the innovation diffusion theory perspective, our findings indicate that perceived advantage, compatibility with existing systems, and the urgent influence of regulatory authorities and stakeholders are essential factors in the diffusion of sustainable technology in air freight.

Systems theory underlines, furthermore, the deep connections between many players in the air freight ecosystem and points out, correspondingly, that sustainability cannot be reached by individual efforts but rather through collaborative strategies across the entire industry. This approach improves the understanding of how the principles of sustainability can be put into practice within dynamic and interconnected systems.

5.2.2. Practical Implications

For industry practitioners, this research stresses the need to implement sustainable technology and operating methods early. The report illustrates how these early adopters benefit from decreased environmental impact and increased operational efficiency, earning a competitive advantage. Companies should concentrate on investments in sustainable aviation fuels (SAFs), energy-efficient ground equipment, and modern logistics systems, assuring both ecological responsibility and long-term profitability.

Policymakers may exploit the information from this research to establish more supportive regulatory frameworks that foster sustainability in the air freight business. By applying a combination of incentives and restrictions, they may speed the sector's shift to greener practices. Additionally, technology companies have considerable possibilities to create solutions specialized to air freight, since our results suggest a rising need for technologies that decrease environmental impact without sacrificing operational effectiveness.

6. CONCLUSION

6.1. Summary of Research

This report offers a detailed review of sustainable practices in the air freight transportation business in Vietnam. Through descriptive statistics, cross-tabulation, pairwise correlations, and linear regression analysis, we revealed critical links between environmental impact assessments, perceived sustainability practices, and the success of sustainability programs. Our results reveal that certain elements, like environmental impact assessments and regulatory backing, greatly affect opinions of sustainable methods. However, the non-normal distribution of residuals highlights possible areas for model development. Overall, the findings show the crucial significance of integrating complete environmental assessments and supporting policies to boost sustainability outcomes in the business.

6.2. Future Research Directions

Future research should address the constraints found in this work, notably the non-normality of residuals, by researching new variables or utilizing different analytical approaches to enhance the model. Further research might study the influence of other variables, such as technical improvements or legislative changes, on sustainable practices in the air freight industry. Expanding the study to encompass a larger variety of businesses or geographic regions might give more generalized insights into sustainability methods and their efficacy. Additionally, longitudinal studies might give significant views on the long-term consequences of sustainability programs and policy changes.

APPENDICES

Appendix A: Survey Questions

Variable name	Question/Statement	Author	Using method
Role	What is your role within the air cargo logistics sector?		
Experience	How many years of experience do you have in the air cargo industry?		
Emissions Measure	How frequently does your organization measure carbon emissions from air cargo operations?	(Bartle, Lutte, & Leuenberger, 2021)	Likert scale
Waste Reduction	To what extent does your organization implement waste reduction practices in air cargo logistics?	(Beškovnik, 2024)	
Tech Importance	How important are sustainable technologies (e.g., energy-efficient ground support equipment) for your organization’s strategic goals?	(Choi, 2023)	
Adoption Barriers	What are the main barriers your organization faces in adopting new sustainable technologies?	(Wang et al., 2023)	
Regulation Effect	How effective do you perceive current government regulations in promoting sustainability within the air cargo sector?	(Trinh et al., 2022)	
Regulation Familiarity	How familiar are you with the international and national regulations related to air cargo sustainability?	(Yu & Luu, 2022)	
Stakeholder Engagement	How frequently does your organization engage with stakeholders (e.g., airlines, regulators, technology providers) to discuss sustainability issues?	(Nguyen & Pham, 2020)	
Regulatory Collaboration	How would you describe the level of collaboration between your organization and regulatory bodies regarding sustainability practices?	(Karanki & Bilotkach, 2024)	

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